

THE ROLE OF HYDROLOGICAL FACTORS IN THE TRANSFORMATION OF LANDSCAPES OF THE ZAGATALA-LAHIJ PHYSICAL GEOGRAPHICAL REGION

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Summary: The Zagatala-Lahij region is a region where various natural processes occur dynamically. Here, hydrological factors, especially the intensive activity of rivers, snowmelt, precipitation and groundwater, play a key role in the formation of landscapes. The river network of the region consists mainly of mountain rivers, which with their rapid flows cause erosion and soil washing. Most of the water flow of the rivers occurs in the spring and summer months. As a result of increased precipitation and rapid snowmelt, the water level of the rivers rises, erosion processes and landslides occur. These changes negatively affect agriculture, reduce soil fertility. In addition, groundwater approaching the surface and swamping are also observed. Due to climate change, the hydrological regime becomes unstable and landscape transformations accelerate.

Key words: Zagatala-Lahij, hydrological factors, river network, precipitation, landslides, groundwater, erosion

The Zagatala-Lahij physical-geographic region is located on the southern slope of the Greater Caucasus (within Azerbaijan). The territory of this region starts from the Georgian border (Mazimchai basin) in the west and extends for 220 km to the Girdimanchay basin in the east. In the north, its border runs along the watershed of the Bash Suayirichi ridge, and in the south along the northern border of the Ganikh-Ayrichay depression.

The widest part of the region is 26 km, in the eastern and western parts, the narrowest part is 10 km, in the center - in the Dashagilchay basin. The watershed of the Greater Caucasus ridge is narrow, consisting of pointed, conical peaks. The passes that cross it cross the same direction through monotonous valleys (Nohurlar, Tinov-Rosso, Dindidag, etc.) or through narrow, saddle-shaped Agbulag, West Salavat, and East Salavat depressions. The highest point of the Greater Caucasus range is 3,400 meters, and the lowest part is up to 2,600 meters in absolute height. Some passages of these mountains, especially in mountain passes, have been inaccessible to humans. In the summer, glaciers exist on the northern slopes of the Bazarduzu, Bazaryurd and Tufan mountains in the high mountains. These glaciers are located at altitudes of 3,600 meters and higher.

Figure 1. Zagatala-Lahij physical geographical region (wikipedia)

Since the landscape structure of the region is diverse, natural processes occur dynamically and intensively here. Along with climate, geological structure, and biotic factors, hydrological factors also play a key role in the formation and transformation of landscapes. Water — both surface and underground — is a leading force in terms of relief erosion, soil erosion, vegetation change, and impact on human settlements. One of them, and perhaps the most influential, is hydrological factors. Hydrological factors mainly include surface and groundwater, river networks, the amount and distribution of precipitation, evaporation, etc.

If we evaluate the general characteristics of the hydrological network in the region, the Zagatala-Lahij physical-geographical region has a very rich and complex structure from a hydrographic point of view. The location of the region on the southern slope of the Greater Caucasus and the mildly humid climatic conditions have created conditions for the formation of a dense and active river network in this area. The water bodies of the region consist mainly of mountain rivers, and these rivers are characterized by high energy, fast flow, and flood regime. The main water arteries that form the hydrographic skeleton of the area - Talachay, Katekhchay, Karachay, Mukhachay and Lahichchay - play an important role in the formation of the natural water cycle landscape structure of the region.

Figure 2. Gabala city-Demiraparan River

These rivers depend mainly on snow and rainwater for their source of nutrition. As a result of intensive snowmelt in the spring and summer months in high mountainous areas and the simultaneous increase in precipitation, the water level in the rivers increases significantly, which leads to the expansion of river channels, deepening of valleys and intensification of erosion processes. It is during these periods that the majority of the annual water flow of the rivers is formed. For example, approximately 60-70 percent of the annual water flow of rivers such as Katekhchay and Talachay falls on April-June.

This intensive activity of rivers has a strong impact on the geomorphological structure of the region. Strong mechanical washings occurring in valleys and slopes lead to thinning of the soil cover, transportation of the fertile layer and accumulation of alluvial washes in the lower parts. As a result of erosion processes, both natural landscapes change and the quality of lands suitable for agriculture decreases. At the same time, under the influence of rivers, landslide zones are sometimes activated, especially in foothill areas, slope stability is disrupted.

It should be noted that these rivers also play an important role in the ecological balance of the region. They regulate the moisture balance of the soil, create specific microclimate conditions in the river valleys and form a favorable habitat for various plants and animals. Thus, the Zagatala-Lahij rivers act not only as a source of irrigation and drinking water, but also as one of the main natural factors in the formation of the relief, soil formation processes and landscape transformation.

The distribution of precipitation in the Zagatala-Lahij physical-geographical region varies depending on the relief of the region, the direction of air masses and the height above sea level. The territory, especially in the mountainous and foothill zones, has indicators close to humid subtropical climate types. The amount of annual precipitation here varies between 1200–1600 mm, which is significantly higher compared to other regions of Azerbaijan. The main amount of precipitation is observed in the spring and autumn months - about 60–70%. Since these periods coincide with both the vegetation stage of vegetation and the waterlogging period of rivers, the amount and intensity of precipitation directly affect the environment.

Monthly and annual values of precipitation distribution on the southern slope of the Greater Caucasus (S.H. Khalilov, S.H. Safarova 2001).

Districts	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	Year
Gabala	49.00	55.30	89.70	102.80	122.40	112.40	74.70	69.70	78.50	126.10	66.660	55.50	1000.80
Oghuz	42.50	49.60	83.60	97.80	104.90	104.90	67.10	57.20	73.70	101.00	72.90	46.80	915.30
Sheki	35.80	43.80	63.40	91.20	103.60	101.10	60.20	56.00	68.10	88.60	57.60	38.10	807.40
Zagatala	38.30	44.60	72.70	102.20	125.40	129.10	77.20	74.00	84.70	100.70	69.70	40.30	958.90

According to meteorological data for 2023, the amount of precipitation recorded in Zagatala in September exceeded the monthly norm by 12%. This led to the fact that the flow capacity exceeded the expected level. Preliminary climate indicators for the period January-April 2024 showed that precipitation in the region exceeded the average multi-year indicators by 15–20%. Such sharp differences, especially in mountainous terrain, resulted in the intensification of hydrological processes.

This excess water loading in river valleys leads to increased erosion, washout, and subsidence. As soon as the rain water reaches the surface, it collects on sloping areas and flows into rivers, carrying with it the upper fertile layer of the soil. Thus, the soil cover suitable for agriculture becomes thinner, its productivity decreases, and in some cases it becomes completely unsuitable for cultivation. The humus layer formed over several decades as a result of the erosion process can be destroyed in a few hours of flooding.

At the same time, precipitation on this scale and the resulting floods also change the geomorphological structure of the relief. The course of rivers can change, new erosion forms - ravines, ravines, landslide zones - appear in old valleys. Such changes have been common in recent years in the agricultural areas of the Zagatala-Lahij region, especially in the foothills. According to residents, crop losses in some areas have reached 20-30%.

Grouping of floodplain river discharge cones

G.Sh. Mammadov and M.Y. Khalilov (2002) believe that areas with sparse vegetation create favorable conditions for the formation of floods. In this case, the soil remains “bare” and erosion accelerates in the area under the influence of exogenous processes, which ultimately creates conditions for the formation of floods. On the contrary, in areas with dense vegetation and weak erosion processes, the activity of floods is also less. Especially in alpine and subalpine meadows, as well as in summer and winter pastures, excessive grazing of livestock weakens the soil, accelerates the erosion process and, as a result, intensifies the activity of floods.

Rich scientific materials on the influence of geological and tectonic conditions on the spread of floods and floodplains on the southern slope of the Greater Caucasus have been collected in the works of various researchers, including I.E. Mardanov (1965), M.O. Mammadalizadeh (1986), Z.A. Hamidova (2011) and others.

Fundamental studies on floods in Azerbaijan were conducted by B.A. Budagov (1963) and I.E. Mardanov (1965). These researchers studied in detail the geomorphological structure of flood-prone river valleys of the Greater Caucasus in their works. According to them, floodplains of natural origin are formed as a result of erosion, landslides, erosion and avalanches, while floodplains of anthropogenic origin are formed under the influence of agricultural and technogenic processes.

The activity of floodplains, which play an important role in the differentiation of the landscape, is mainly related to the composition of the rocks located in the basins. The occurrence of flood events and their recurrence frequency in the study area varies depending on the characteristics of the landscape belts. The source of nutrition for floods is mainly landslides and landslide masses formed on sandy-clayey rocks of the Paleogene-Neogene period. In basins where clayey shales of the Jurassic period are widespread, the active development of floodplains is accompanied by strong denudation processes. Similar floodplains are clearly observed in the upper part of the Saribaş village, as well as along the tributaries of the Kurmuk River. In particular, floodplains in the Bulanısu River basin, where Jurassic shales are widespread, are more dynamic than floodplains in the tributaries of the Agsu and Kunaxaysu rivers, where limestones of the Cretaceous period predominate. Active floodplains provide the main material for the formation of flood flows in the areas between the Mukhaxchay and Filfilichai rivers.

According to R.H. Dashdiyev (2004), by studying the degree of impact of flood flows on natural terrain complexes and taking into account their current state, it is possible to identify four main levels of dynamism in the southern slopes of the Greater Caucasus. These levels are distinguished as highly

dynamic, moderately dynamic and weakly dynamic landscapes. Each level differs from the others due to its internal characteristics. The dynamism of landscapes on the southern slope of the Greater Caucasus increases from the foothills of the alluvial cones to the peaks, due to the intensification of geomorphological processes in that direction and the rejuvenation of landscapes.

According to the research of M. Mammadov and F. Imanov (2003), the basin area of mountain rivers where flood events are recorded mainly varies in the range of 100–300 km². The average annual water discharge in these rivers is 3–15 m³/sec, and the gradient is between 0.01–0.1. During low-water periods, the average flow velocity is 1–2.5 m/sec, and the depth varies in the range of 0.3–1 m. During flood events, hydrodynamic indicators increase significantly - the flow velocity increases to 3–5 m/sec, and the depth increases to 3–4 m. Under such conditions, the specific gravity of the flood mass is on average 1.8 tons/m³, and in some cases this indicator varies in the range of 1.9–2.3 tons/m³.

On the southern slope of the Greater Caucasus, the altitudinal-spatial differentiation of landscapes is observed against the background of a gradual rise in relief. The distribution and differentiation of floodplains within vertical landscape zones is of great importance both from a scientific and applied point of view. Research conducted in this area allows us to study the regularities of the formation and development of floodplains, as well as to obtain important scientific results aimed at weakening their impact. The mentioned processes cover large areas, especially in the areas selected as the object of research.

The high mountain zones of the Zagatala-Lahij physical-geographical region are characterized by intensive snowfalls, especially in the winter months. Villages located in this region - including settlements such as Alibay, Suayril, Siliban and Mazikh - remain under snow cover during the winter season, sometimes lasting several months. According to meteorological observations for November 2023, the thickness of the snow cover in the village of Alibay reached 17 cm, which is an indicator higher than the average multi-year norm. Such a high snow cover is of particular importance not only in terms of atmospheric precipitation, but also in terms of hydrological and geomorphological changes that will occur in the future.

In the spring season – especially in March and April – the process of snowmelt accelerates. In March 2024, the average snow depth on the southern slopes of the Greater Caucasus increased to 25 cm in some places. As a result of the rapid melting of this snow mass, the risk of floods and landslides in river basins significantly increased, and a number of local hydrological events were recorded in early April. A sharp increase in surface runoff intensified erosion processes in the riverbeds, caused soil layers to be washed away and flooded areas to expand. In March-April 2025, warmer than normal weather in the mountains led to rapid snowmelt. In particular, the water level in the Karachay and Mukhaxchay basins reached critical levels, and flooding of agricultural fields was observed in some local areas. The washing power of water in rivers increased, and the supporting parts of some bridges were damaged.

At the same time, such water loading results in the formation of micro-relief forms in valleys and slopes. As a result of the high speed of water flow, soil erosion, the formation of small ravines and deep erosion beds are observed. This process gradually results in a change in the landscape structure and reduces the productivity of the soil cover. As a result of water accumulation, especially in the foothills, water saturation occurs in the soil layer, which increases the likelihood of landslides.

The sharp slopes in the relief of the Zagatala-Lahij region also create favorable conditions for landslides. With the combined effect of precipitation and snowmelt, water seeps into the deep layers of the soil, causing the separation of rocks and massive soil movements. In May 2023, such a landslide was recorded around the villages of Mukhax and Gabizdara, as a result of which village roads were closed and some agricultural areas were seriously damaged. These events once again prove that hydrological factors are not limited to short-term flooding and erosion, but also lead to long-term morphological changes.

In the foothills of the territory, another problem is observed - waterlogging and waterlogging of the soil as a result of groundwater approaching the surface. This is especially evident around the villages of Bahmetli, Yukhari Tala and Yengiyan. Aeration in water-saturated soils weakens, soil

microflora changes, and agricultural productivity sharply decreases. The typical meadow and forest plants that previously developed on these soils begin to be replaced by hydrophilic - that is, water-loving - plants over time, which leads to significant structural changes in the vegetation cover and biogeosystems.

On the other hand, population growth and expansion of agricultural activities in the region have necessitated the development of irrigation systems. However, improper planning of these systems, changes in river courses, and uncontrolled construction of dams and canals lead to an uneven distribution of water resources. As a result, in some areas, soil salinization and waterlogging are observed, while in other areas, drought and cracked soils are observed. This is an indicator of anthropogenic transformation of landscapes in the area.

Finally, global climate change in recent decades has also had a serious impact on the hydrological regime of this region. With an increase in average annual temperatures of 1–1.3°C, evaporation has increased and an imbalance in the moisture balance has emerged. These changes have changed the periods of snow cover formation and melting, disrupted the rhythm of precipitation distribution, and made the annual regime of river flow unstable. All these factors, taken together, act as one of the main reasons for the continuous change of the Zagatala–Lahij landscapes in recent years.

RESULTS

1. Hydrological factors play a key role in the formation of landscapes - rivers, groundwater and precipitation directly affect the relief and land cover.

2. The river network of the region consists of mountain rivers and has a flood regime - this enhances processes such as erosion and soil washing.

3. Strong surface runoff washes away the fertile layer of the soil and harms agriculture - productivity decreases, areas unsuitable for cultivation are created.

4. Landslides and subsidence are more often observed in the foothills - this is also associated with a violation of slope stability.

5. Snow cover forms a thick layer in winter and, when it melts rapidly in spring, increases the risk of floods - which also causes geomorphological changes in river basins.

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